

FAIR2Adapt

Zoom link (Tuesday and Wednesday)

Join Zoom Meeting:

<https://simula.zoom.us/j/63503520807?pwd=37Palb2claiKGUd84uSal5pAEJALgh.1>

Meeting ID: 635 0352 0807

Passcode: 070094

Preparation Meeting (WP2-WP6 leaders & experts)

Monday 13 January 10:00-17:00

13 January 10:00-17:00		
10:00-17:00	<p><u>Alignments between technical & community WP leaders.</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• WP2: Core FDO Infrastructure• WP3: FDO-driven FAIRification Framework• WP4: User-facing knowledge Services in Support for CCA• WP5: Community Support and Engagement• WP6: Case studies and end-user applications	<p>Leaders from WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 & additional experts (as requested by WP leads)</p> <p>WP2: Raul Palma (PSNC) (requested Manolis NKUA)</p> <p>WP3: Daniel Garijo (UPM) (requested Jose from Expert.ai)</p> <p>WP4: Markus Stocker (TIB)</p> <p>WP5: Barbara Magagna (GFF)</p> <p>WP6: Tiago Capela Lourenço (FC.ID)</p>

Kick-off Meeting (all)

Day-1: Tuesday 14 January

14 January 9:30-17:30		
09:30-10:00	<p><u>Arrival and Gathering on the 8th Floor – Logistics:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Please arrive at Simula early enough to ensure you reach the room on time. The session will begin promptly at 10:00! 	
10:00-10:30 5' 20'	<p><u>FAIR2Adapt Opening Session:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome statement - Simula Research Laboratory Words from the Project Officer 	SRL Gustavo Naumann
10:30-10:50 10' 10'	<p><u>FAIR2Adapt Introduction:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> FAIR2Adapt Introduction (Consortium, Governance, Code of Conduct, Objectives, Communities and Case studies) FAIR2Adapt Technical Management 	Louise & Anne
10:50-11:00	Break	
11:00-12:00 45' max + 15' Q&A	<p><u>Invited Keynotes:</u> Implementing FAIR Principles in the ACTRIS Data Centre: Advancing FAIRness in the Atmospheric Subdomain, Cathrine Lund Myhre, Senior Scientist and Head of Section for Data Centre Services at NILU, and leader of the ACTRIS Data Centre: <i>The Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS) is a pan-European research infrastructure producing high-quality data and information on short-lived atmospheric constituents and on the processes leading to the variability of these constituents in natural and controlled atmospheres. This keynote talk will outline the journey of integrating FAIR principles within the ACTRIS Data Centre (DC), highlighting milestones and achievements, challenges, and lessons learned. Additionally, it will explore efforts to converge FAIR practices within the atmospheric subdomain and across environmental RIs, illustrating how this work supports science and adaptation to climate change.</i></p> <p>See full abstract here.</p>	Cathrine Lund Myhre/Markus Fiebig (NILU, Norway)
12:00-13:00	Lunch - Group picture	
13:00-14:00 10'+ 5' Q&A 10'+ 5' Q&A 10'+ 5' Q&A 10'+ 5' Q&A (1 hour max)	<p><u>FAIR2Adapt strategic alignment:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The EOSC and EOSC partnership (EOSC Association) The mission Adaptation to Climate Change Adapting to Climate Risks in Hamburg: Integration of FAIR2Adapt Use Cases into the Urban Data Platform Alignment with FAIR2Adapt and FAIR2Adapt CCA Communities 	Ute Gunsenheimer Guido Schmidt City of Hamburg SRL/GFF/all

14:00-14:45 10' 30' (5'-per case study) 5' Q&A	<u>Technical Work-Package Presentation:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● WP6: Case studies and end-user applications <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CS1 : Spread of radioactive isotopes in the arctic ○ CS2: River-dominated Ocean Margins ○ CS3: Hamburg city ○ CS4: FAIR-by-design national adaptation hub ○ CS5: The connectivity Hub and weADAPT ○ CS6: EU taxonomy for sustainable activities 	Tiago Torill Tina Malte Tiago Sukaina Julia/Christian
14:45-15:45 12' per WP + 3' Q/A	<u>Technical Work-Package Presentation:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● WP2: Core FDO Infrastructure ● WP3: FDO-driven FAIRification Framework ● WP4: User-facing knowledge Services in Support for CCA ● WP5: Community Support and Engagement 	Raul Daniel Markus Barbara
15:45-16:00	Break	
16:00-17:00	<u>Breakout session - Day 1:</u> Ice-breaking session Specific objectives and results (bring your own perspectives/expectations to discuss them) Ethical aspects, scientific advisory board, stakeholder group, etc.	All
17:00-17:30	<u>Reporting back from the Breakout sessions (in the plenary)</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● One short summary per group ● Q&A and wrap-up day 1 	All
17:30	End of 1 st -day meeting	
18.30	Depart from Simula reception - Walk together to Social event	All
19.00 – 22:30	Social event – drinks + light dinner	All

Day-2: Wednesday 15 January

15 January 9:00-14:30		
8:30- 9:00	<u>Arrival and Gathering on the 8th Floor – Logistics:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Please arrive at Simula early enough to ensure you reach the room on time. The session will begin promptly at 9:00! 	
9:00-9:15	Opening – Planning work tasks	
9:15-10:15	<u>Breakout session Day 2 – Slides Instruction and Example</u> Work-Package and Task fine-grained planning, Data management and data processing, Case Study requirements analysis, ...	All
10:15-10:30	Break	

10:30-11:00	Administrative aspects – Tools, Reporting, PMP	Louise Bolands Eklund
11:00-12:00 10' per WP 10' discussion	<u>Reporting & discussion from breakout session: Work-Package fine-grained planning and organization</u> Findings and restitution per WP <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● WP2: Core FDO Infrastructure ● WP3: FDO-driven FAIRification Framework ● WP4: User-facing knowledge Services in Support for CCA ● WP5: Community Support and Engagement ● WP6: Case studies and end-user applications 	WP leaders Raul Daniel Markus Barbara Tiago
12:00-13:00	Lunch	
13:00-13:05	Introduction of WP7: Communication, Dissemination, Sustainability and Exploitation	Claudia/Riccardo
13:05-13:45	WP7: Communication & Dissemination	Alexandra/Michael
13:45-14:15	WP7: Exploitation, cooperation with EOOSC & the mission adaptation to climate change	Claudia/Riccardo
14:15-14:30	<u>FAIR2Adapt Closing Session:</u> Conclusions, Announcement of next dates <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FAIR2Adapt Time capsule 	Anne
14:30	End of 2 nd day Meeting	

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Travel information whilst in Oslo

Key locations (see map below):

Blue pin: Simula Research Laboratory, Kristian Augusts gate 23, 0164 Oslo.

Red pin: Restaurant

How to reach Simula from Oslo Airport (Gardermoen):

We strongly recommend booking your flights to Gardermoen (OSL) and not Torp. There are several ways of getting from Gardermoen to Oslo:

- One is the airport express train [Flytoget \(flytoget.no\)](http://flytoget.no) which has quite an expensive travel fare, but will bring you to Oslo's central train station in about 20 minutes.
- There are also [regular local Trains \(vy.no\)](http://vy.no) that can transport you to the centre of town. These have cheaper fares, but run less often and might take slightly more time.

The express train (Flytoget) takes around 20 minutes and will bring you to Nationaltheatret station in the center of Oslo, which is very close to the hotels and the Simula office. Alternatively, you can get off at the central station (Oslo S or Sentralstasjon), which may be a better option if your hotel is closer to that station.

Local transportation:

- To plan your journey within Oslo (if you do not want to walk), Information can be found at <https://ruter.no/en/> . To buy tickets, we strongly suggest you download the ruter app on your phone.

